

TEACHERS' TURNOUT INDICATORS OF ONE OF THE PRIVATE SCHOOLS IN LEYTE

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ABSTRACT

The study is quantitative research that aims to analyze the indicators that influenced teachers' turnout in FCIC. There were 37 former tenured teachers from AY 2000 to 2018 as respondents to the study. It also assesses the satisfaction and dissatisfaction level of teachers in terms of working conditions, career path development, and compensation. Results as to socio-demographic profile in terms of length of service show that they are significant and thus affect their turnout. As to respondents' priorities in life, their families are their responsibilities. As to respondents' family conditions which means being the breadwinner in the family is one of the factors influencing their turnout. In terms of satisfaction level in their working conditions and career path development as to the indicators on administrative support, professional advancement & development, and training & seminar enhancement, former tenured teachers were satisfied. On the indicators of the relationship with colleagues, personal & spiritual growth development, and the salary was on time the former tenured teachers were delighted. However, the dissatisfaction level as to the indicators on merits and awards, student attitude, and the teaching load, educational & technical advancement, and promotion & career growth goals, salary adequately met the needs of the teachers and salary was equitable to the job the former tenured teachers were dissatisfied. Finally, they were highly dissatisfied with the salary indicator comparable to the public school. Furthermore, a significant relationship was found out among the socio-demographic profile, priority in life, and family condition. Moreover, there is a significant difference among the indicators of working conditions, career path development, and compensation. The results revealed that respondents need security and improvement in their careers.

Keywords: *Teachers' turnout, indicators, minimize turnout*

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INTRODUCTION

Teachers are indeed the front liners and the backbone of any educational institution whether private or public school. They play an important role in the holistic development of the students in all aspects: physical, emotional, psychological, biological, intellectual, and spiritual development. The success of any school is directly related to the ability and skills of hired teachers. The growth and success of any school are decisively influenced by the commitment and loyalty of teachers toward their work (Kumar, 2018). Indeed, schools do not only consider high intelligence as the sole criterion in hiring teachers but also having the right work ethics.

Inevitably, teachers' turnout becomes a local problem and a global challenge. By its very nature, teachers' turnout is extremely a complex phenomenon. Despite the school's intention to hold the teachers, various indicators affect their decisions to stay. The Philippines is also among the countries that are experiencing a constant turnout of teachers, especially in the basic education level. It is frequently positioned as either a problem for workforce planning and resources or as an indicator of the relatively poor quality of schooling and teacher morale. Teachers' turnout reduces the number of teachers available to schools, potentially exacerbating localized teachers' shortage (Waititu, 2013).

One of the primary concerns and challenges of Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception, Baybay, Leyte, Incorporated is the growing teachers' shortage every year in the Basic Education Department. This problem affects the educational system of the school. The lack of sufficient, qualified teachers and staff instability threaten students' ability to learn and reduce teachers' effectiveness, and high teachers' turnout consumes economic resources that could be better deployed elsewhere. The teachers' shortage makes it more difficult to build a solid reputation for teaching and to professionalize it, which further contributes to perpetuating the shortage (Weiss, 2019). Based on informal feedback, a few reasons why teachers left are due to salary and compensation, heavy academic load and relationship issues, however, these are yet to be studied and proven. In the truest sense, the economic satisfaction in the teaching profession cannot be underrated for it supports the personal and needs of the family. Low remuneration contributes directly to the high turnout of teachers to a large extent. Furthermore, the heavy teaching load leaves the teachers "emotionally drained" and other perceived teaching profession as less attractive whose work condition is challenging compared to other professions. Braid (2015) asserts that the workload of the teachers is a critical factor that affects the quality of learning. With this contention, Braid cites further that factors that motivate teachers to engage in a long-term teaching career should be considered.

It is in this premise that the study is being thought to minimize the turnout of teachers every school year and to help the school reduce expenses in re-training and re-tooling newly hired teachers for the particular school year. Instead, budget for particular training and seminars can be allocated to other need areas such as augmenting teachers' salary, additional incentives, and other benefits that will hold the teachers to stay and to continue their services in FCIC.

This study will benefit the teachers as issues causing the high turnout will be addressed accordingly. Their continued services will encourage parents to let their children pursue their High School education because of the assured quality training their children will acquire from more seasoned and experienced teachers. In like manner, students will increase their motivation to study, develop and enhance their skills because of equally good and competent teachers.

Statement of the Problem

This study analyzed the indicators that influenced teachers' turnout in the Basic Education Department of FCIC. Specifically, it sought to answer the following problems:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 1. Age
 2. Sex
 3. Civil Status
 4. Length of Service
 5. Degree/Programs Earned?
2. What is the respondents' priority in life and family conditions?
3. What is the satisfaction level of teachers in terms of:
 - a. Working Conditions
 - b. Career Path Development
 - c. Compensation?
4. Is there a significant relationship between socio-demographic profile, priority and family conditions, and the satisfaction level of teachers?
5. Is there a significant difference among the indicators influencing teachers' turnout in terms of:
 - a. Working Conditions
 - b. Career Path Development
 - c. Compensation?
6. What faculty development program can be designed to minimize teachers' turnout?

METHODOLOGY

The Sample and Locale of the Study

The study conducted an extensive review of the socio-demographic profile of the respondents specifically former tenured teachers in the basic education department of the Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception, Baybay, Leyte, Incorporated from the academic year 2000 to 2018. The complete enumeration of the respondents was used and was conducted in the Elementary and High Schools of Baybay District in Baybay City Division, Baybay City, Leyte, and its neighboring public elementary and high school districts in Leyte under DepEd. The distribution of respondents is reflected in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

Number of Years in Service at FCIC Total Number of Tenured Teachers (Exclusive Years 2000-2018) Who Left FCIC		
15 years to 19 years	(1999-2004)	3
10 years to 14 years	(2004-2009)	3
5 years to 9 years	(2015-2018)	11
0 year to 4 years	(2009-2015)	20
TOTAL		37

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, length of service, and degree/program earned is presented in Table 2. The result was determined through the data obtained from the 37 former tenured teachers of FCIC specifically from the basic education department who are now employed in DepEd as the respondents in this study. The following table shows the distribution of socio-demographic profiles, respondents' priorities, and family conditions. The satisfaction and dissatisfaction levels of the teachers on working conditions, career path development, and compensation are also presented in the table.

Table 2. Distribution of Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents

<i>Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents</i>			
A. Age	No. of Respondent (37)	Frequency	Percentage
	Below 30 years old	16	43%
	31-40 years old	20	54%
	41 – above years old	1	3%
B. Sex	No. of Respondent (37)	Frequency	Percentage
	Male	9	24%
	Female	28	76%
C. Civil Status	No. of Respondent (37)	Frequency	Percentage
	Single	21	57%
	Married	16	43%
D. Length of Service	No. of Respondent (37)	Frequency	Percentage
	Below 4 years	20	54%
	5-9 years	11	30%
	10-14 years	3	8%
	15 – above years	3	8%
E. Degree Earned	No. of Respondent (37)	Frequency	Percentage
	Doctorate Degree	20	54%
	Master's Degree	11	30%
	Bachelor Degree	3	8%
	Any other	3	8%

Age

In terms of age, based on the data in Table 2, out of 37 teachers, 20 (54%) were 31-40 years old, the most dominant age level among the respondents. The result shows that most of the teachers were already older. The older teachers could connect with students. Since they are at the right age, they can easily mingle with their students, they can easily understand their students, and can give a better quality of education. The bottom line is that passion and love for teaching have no barriers and this means that age is not a guarantee for teachers to stay.

Agyemen (2014) contends that as teachers age, higher turnout rates increase as a result of shifting career paths. Their needs increase for their security in life, flexibility to relocate, and fewer family responsibilities and financial obligations to support the growing needs of their families. The age of teachers plays an important part in teachers' commitment, being rooted in the job, psychological contract, and the decision to leave.

Sex

As shown in Table 2, of the 37 teachers, nine (24 percent) were males and twenty-eight (76 percent) were females. The result shows that the teaching force in FCIC was dominated by female teachers. This means that females had the highest number of teacher applicants and qualified for a teaching position in FCIC. However, female teachers also appear to have the best relationships with all students, regardless of gender according to Darling-Hammond (2017). The number of women outnumbers the men in the elementary and high school departments. The truth is, the teaching force of FCIC was dominated by women specifically in the grade school department. The high female teacher percentages have been consistent over several decades from 2000 to the present.

Civil Status

The socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of civil status is reflected in Table 2, of the 37 teachers, twenty-one (57 percent) were singles, and sixteen (43 percent) were married. The result means that almost all of the teachers who left FCIC were singles almost equal to married teachers. This means that the school did not only hire single teachers but also considered the application of married teachers to complete the teaching force of FCIC based on their qualifications in the teaching position. The civil status of the teachers has a greater impact on the part of the student learning process. Teachers' qualifications and determination either single or married are very important to student academic performance and achievement. As expressed by Alshutwi (2017) effective and determined single young teachers were likely to leave their teaching position looking for more opportunities in the public or other companies.

Length of Service

The socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of length of service as shown in Table 2, of the 37 teachers, revealed that twenty (54 percent) of the teachers had below 5 years of teaching experience in the academic year 2015-2016. Eleven (30 percent) of the teachers had 5 to 9 years of their teaching experience in the academic year 2014-2015. This result is attributed to the fact that the majority of teachers' turnout started in the academic year 2014-2016 with 5 years below teaching experience. The length of service reflects the actual situation of the teaching force of FCIC where teachers gained enough experience and training that made them more qualified to the public school. They were so aware that their experience and the certificate of training are the topmost qualifications in public school-based on the result of the informal group discussion. According to Waititu (2013), the number of years the teacher spends in school is not an assurance that they will stay permanently.

Degree Earned

Results revealed that thirty-five (94 percent) of the teachers had bachelor's degrees. This result realistically describes that the majority of the teaching force of FCIC Basic Education is predominantly bachelor's degree holders. This result is attributed to the fact that a Bachelor's degree is a requirement in teaching. During the time of their employment, they were mostly new graduates. Data revealed that there was only one (3 percent) teacher who has a master's unit who left FCIC. With or without master's units earned do not guarantee that teachers will stay. The Bachelor's degree is one of the bases of their qualification in applying to any school. Making the world a better place starts with a bachelor's degree or master's degree holder. According to Haddad (2010), the rates of turnout do not match with individual's degree earned. The teachers are bound to look for greener pastures and find ways of improving their skills by going into further studies to increase their competencies in anticipation that this will help them get a job with higher returns.

Respondents' Priority in Life and Family Conditions

Respondents' priority in life refers to family, professional growth/promotion, relationship with colleagues, and salary/income while family condition includes being the breadwinner or not a breadwinner in their family and the number of dependents they have. These variables may influence teachers' turnout. The result is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Respondents Priority in Life and Family Conditions

<i>Priority in Life and Family Conditions</i>			
A. Priority in Life	No. of Respondent (37)	Frequency	Percentage
	Family	34	92%
	Professional Growth/Promotion	1	3%
	Relationship with Colleagues	0	0%
	Salary/Income	2	5%
B. Family Conditions	Breadwinner (2-5 no. of dependents)	22	60%
	Noa Breadwinner	15	40%

The respondents expressed that their family is their priority and the reason for turnout. They are family-oriented teachers who always look out for the best interest of their family and usually settle down their personal needs. Based on the result of the focus group discussion, money matters. Money is always a difficult topic to discuss and can cause misunderstandings even to the closest families. Nevertheless, their loyalty to their family always brings about a feeling of satisfaction and security. More often than not, they put them as their top priority. The family doesn't usually mean blood relatives, but it is always nice to know that there are people who are always at their back no matter what. According to Metha (2012), family conditions comprise a bigger part of a person's defined character. The respondents' family conditions such as family problems, issues, and status are often the reasons for the turnout of teachers either by retirement or resignation. Ingersoll (2014) supports the stand that teachers' personality contributes to overall effectiveness in classroom teaching. For family conditions, twenty-two (60 percent) claimed that they are the breadwinner in the family and obligated to spend on the needs of the family. Their salary would not be sufficient to cater to more than three to five dependents or children including the financial needs of other relatives. They are obliged to help and support each other even financially. One of the values that Filipinos are

known for is “close family ties.” Mutune (2014) supports that work-family facilitation and family satisfaction have a significant positive impact on teachers’ turnout tendencies. The work-family facilitation of family support work not only directly affects the turnout of teachers but also indirectly influences affective commitment.

Satisfaction Level of the Respondents

A general view of the responses to the structured items in the questionnaire was important in analyzing the satisfaction level of those indicators of teachers’ turnout in the basic education at FCIC. The variables include the working conditions with the following indicators administrative support, merits and awards, relationship with colleagues, student attitudes, and teaching. Career path development is another variable with indicators of educational & technical advancement, personal & spiritual growth development, professional advancement & development, promotion & career growth goals, and training & seminar enhancement. While compensation the last variable with the indicators on salary adequately met the needs of the teachers, the salary was comparable to the public school, the salary was equitable to the job, and the salary was on time. Respondents’ satisfaction is a positive or pleasant emotional state resulting from a teacher’s appreciation of their job or experience. The level of teachers’ satisfaction affects positively the school system and brings up successful students. The satisfaction levels were highly satisfied and satisfied as the indicators of teachers’ turnout were categorized to fully meet the expectation and moderately meet the expectation. The other level was highly dissatisfied and dissatisfied as the indicators of teachers’ turnout were categorized as hardly meeting the expectations and did not fully meet the expectations of the respondents in terms of working conditions, career path development, and compensation.

Working Conditions

Table 4a. Distribution of the Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction Level of Teachers on Working Conditions

Indicators	Mean	Satisfaction Level	Description
1. Administrative Support	2.78	Satisfied	The indicators moderately met the expectation of the respondents.
2. Merits and Awards	2.14	Dissatisfied	The indicators hardly met the expectations of the respondents.
3. Relationship with Colleagues	3.43	Highly Satisfied	The indicators fully met the expectation of the respondents.
4. Student Attitude	2.19	Dissatisfied	The indicators hardly met the expectation of the respondents.
5. Teaching Load	2.46	Dissatisfied	The indicators hardly met the expectation of the respondents.

Total	2.60	Satisfied	The indicators moderately met the expectations of the respondents.
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On the working conditions, the data revealed in Table 4a mean of 2.60 which means that the indicators moderately met the expectations of the respondents. However out of five indicators of the working conditions three of these were dissatisfied which means that the indicator hardly met the expectations of the respondents.

As to the indicator on merits and awards, the respondents were dissatisfied which means that this indicator hardly met their expectations. This means that the teacher did not feel any recognition of their extra performance in school since teachers are engaged in multitasking in the classroom. The merits and awards should be suited to the work that teachers do. They need to be recognized for their job well done.

In terms of students' attitudes, the respondents encountered problems basically in the high school department. They were dissatisfied based on the result. This means that the greatest number of students belong to the higher-class level of living and are well off but did not fully experience quality time from their parents. Family and environmental factors also affect student behavior.

While in the indicator of teaching loads, respondents were dissatisfied. This means that teachers' workload was not well compensated which leads to their turnout. This was observed by Tickle, Chang, & Kim (2011) that working conditions are considered the main source of teachers' job dissatisfaction and teachers' turnout. Furthermore, Ladd (2011) cites that many teachers leave their jobs due to a lack of merits and awards, student attitudes, and teaching load. This could mean that unrecognized efforts, and attitude problems of students such as laziness, demotivation, and heavy teaching load cause teachers burnout compelling them to give up their profession.

However, the respondents gave the highest weighted mean of 3.43 in the satisfaction level to the indicator which stated relationship with colleagues which means that the indicator fully met the expectation of the respondents. The respondents were highly satisfied when it comes to their relationship with colleagues. They displayed a good relationship, they were able to spend time together at the workplace harmoniously, especially during faculty in-service and in any team-building activities. A good relationship with colleagues reduces tension and stress at the workplace and makes the environment free and comfortable to work with. This, in turn, enhances efficiency at work.

Meanwhile, the indicator concerning administrative support has a weighted mean of 2.78 which means that the indicator moderately met the expectations of the respondents. The administrations do not support the professional growth of their teachers by just sending them to seminars and training but they supported also their moral, spiritual, and most specifically financial needs. The school administration is extending their help and support in case of financial problems and health emergencies among the teachers. This is contrary to the claims of Ladd (2011) that many teachers leave their jobs due to a lack of administrative support and relationship problems with colleagues. This contention was supported by the ideas of Kraft, Marinell, & Shein-Wei Yee (2016) that relationships with colleagues and administrative support have been reported to be more critical and have a greater effect on teachers' turnover. However, these were not observed by the teachers during their stay in FCIC.

Therefore, improving workplace conditions is an important strategy for school success. Thus, investments to improve workplace conditions will have greater and longer-lasting benefits for the teachers to stay, improve teachers' quality, and effective teaching all point to a set of workplace conditions as potential levers for success. The workplace conditions matter to most of the former tenured teachers in FCIC who are now connected at DepEd.

Career Path Development

Table 4b. Distribution of the Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction Level of Teachers on Career Path Development

Indicators	Mean	Satisfaction Level	Description
1. Educational & Technical Advancement	2.46	Dissatisfied	The indicators hardly met the expectation of the respondents.
2. Personal & Spiritual Growth Development	3.78	Highly Satisfied	The indicators fully met the expectation of the respondents.
3. Professional Advancement and Development	2.86	Satisfied	The indicators moderately met the expectations of the respondents
4. Promotional & Career Growth Goals	1.81	Dissatisfied	The indicators hardly met the expectation of the respondents.
5. Training & Seminar Enhancement	2.84	Satisfied	The indicators moderately met the expectations of the respondents
Total	2.80	Satisfied	The indicators moderately met the expectations of the respondents.

In terms of the career path development of teachers, the weighted mean was 2.80 disclosing the respondents' claim that they were satisfied which means that the indicator moderately met the expectations of the respondents. As presented in Table 4b two out of five indicators had been rated by the respondents as dissatisfied. These are on the educational and technical advancement with a mean was 2.46 and promotion and career growth goals with a mean of 1.81.

For educational and technical advancement, the respondents were dissatisfied. Their dissatisfaction as expressed by respondents is because even if they excel at their jobs in the school, participate in out-of-classroom programs, exhibit leadership qualities, and display a strong command of their subject areas they are not given the chance to advance in their educational and technical skills. They were not given the opportunity to advance to

administrative positions in the school. In this matter, the school has enough religious personnel to hold an office and minimal administrative positions were given to the lay teachers.

In terms of promotion and career growth goals, the respondents were dissatisfied. They were dissatisfied due to the less opportunity given to them to be promoted in a certain office and to their related field in the school instead they were required to earn a master's degree before qualifying for such position in the school. Teachers who wished to advance in their careers were not permitted to take a master's degree within the school year due to their school hectic schedules.

However, the respondents claimed that they were satisfied with their professional advancement and development and with training and seminars enhancement. The school provided all the needed professional advancement and development, training, and seminars enhancement to all qualified teachers with or without experience every year to equip teachers with knowledge and skills for their field of teaching. The school will allocate a budget for retooling and orienting the teachers every school year. The monthly faculty in-service training and seminars in and out of campus have enriched the respondents in their professional advancement and development. The indicators fully met the expectations of the respondents because when attending seminars or official business for the school, an allowance per day will be given by the school. This allowance covers the registration fee, travel, and meals during the seminars, provided the venue is at a reasonable distance. Expenses for seminars outside the province are at the discretion of the School Director. (Administration, Faculty, and Non-Teaching Personnel Manual, Sec. 3.1. B.5).

In terms of personal and spiritual growth development, the respondents claimed that they were highly satisfied. As practiced, FCIC was able to cater to train personal and spiritual growth through faculty benefits and privileges for staff development through the following: Christian Dimension, to strengthen the sacramental and spiritual life of the faculty; Days of Recollection and Retreats are conducted once a year to detach teachers from the earthly self for a moment and examine spiritual failures as well as gains; First Friday Masses with the administration, faculty, and students; Monthly Eucharistic Celebrations or Prayer Services which allow the faculty members the opportunity to gain experience as sponsors, readers, leaders, and officers at religious services; Time for Individual Confessions is made available once a month and occasional Bible sharing are opportunities to enrich understanding and meaning of the words of God. (Administration, Faculty, and Non-Teaching Personnel Manual, Sec. 3.1. C.10). But, Gomez (2014), states that teacher turnout is worrisome and even more challenging to any employer who spends for recruitment, interview, and training newly hired employees, not to mention that these employees may be less adept at their jobs compared to the experienced teachers. Moreover, Gomez cites that career development programs can address these concerns to reduce teacher turnover. The improvement in the educational and technical advancement of teachers provides opportunities that focus on their career path development for the improvement of their instruction in ways consistent with school standards. Thus, teachers may experience a sense of professional growth and satisfaction. To retain good teachers, the school should provide advancement opportunities so that teachers can take steps on their own to open doors to advancement in their careers. Knowing the possibilities helps teachers to get ahead, which often gives them greater professional satisfaction and more pay so they will continue their service to the school.

Compensation

Table 4c. Distribution of the Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction Level of Teachers on Compensation

Indicators	Mean	Satisfaction Level	Description
1. Salary Adequately Met the Needs of the Teachers	1.95	Dissatisfied	The indicators hardly met the expectation of the respondents.
2. Salary was Comparable to the Public School	1.51	Highly Dissatisfied	The indicators did not fully meet the expectation of the respondents.
3. Salary was Equitable to the Job	2.11	Dissatisfied	The indicators hardly met the expectation of the respondents.
4. Salary was on Time	3.70	Highly Satisfied	The indicators fully met the expectation of the respondents.
Total	2.32	Dissatisfied	The indicators hardly met the expectation of the respondents.

On the area of compensation, the result in Table 4c showed a mean of 2.32 indicating the level of dissatisfaction or the indicators hardly met the expectations of the respondents. From the four indicators, the respondents indicated dissatisfaction level in three indicators. The respondents gave the highest weighted mean of 1.51 on the indicator which is salary was highly dissatisfied which shows FCIC is low compared to teachers' salary in the public school. It also appends that the indicator on a salary that adequately met the needs of the teachers has a weighted mean of 1.95, and another with the indicator on a salary which equitable to the job has an equal-weighted mean of 2.11 showing a level of dissatisfaction which the indicator did not meet the expectations of the respondents.

As to salary adequately met the needs of the teachers this means that they were not paid adequately and that they were rarely provided with non-financial incentives. It is obvious from the focus group discussion that the sustainability of teachers will almost be guaranteed in a climate where teachers' job security, infrastructure, and teaching resources, as well as financial incentives, are guaranteed.

In terms of salary equitable to the job means that their compensation is not equitable to the number of years of experience they have in school. Their expectations were not realized as more experience results in a higher pay scale. The unfulfilled needs, goals, and value expectations, as well as the lack of achievement of outcomes, account for job dissatisfaction. However, the school is guided by the existing policy on salary scales for teachers and even gives more than the computed percentage of salary.

This is because private school salary cannot equate with the salary in the public school. This means that the respondents were aware of the salary scale of FCIC but still, they were

trying to render their service to be part of the school system and hoping for an increase whenever they will continue their service to the school for another academic year. Besides, the school cannot solicit from their benefactors outside the Philippines for an increase in teachers' salaries. The compensation offered by the public schools attracts more teachers to transfer causing much turnout in most private schools specifically in FCIC.

However, the respondents gave a weighted mean of 3.70 a satisfaction level as highly satisfied with salary in terms of punctuality in releasing the salary to its employees including teachers. The result means that the indicator fully met the expectations of the respondents. The respondents were highly satisfied when it comes to salary on time. This means that the school prepares the salary for the teachers every 15th and 30th of the month. Whenever the 15th and 30th days fall on Saturday, the salary is given on Friday, while it falls on Sunday, the salary is given on Monday. Another benefit for teachers is through cash advances which can be liquidated in terms agreed upon between the teacher and the Treasurer. A cash advance may not be made until after the first salary payment in June nor after March 31 at the end of the school year, however, the school can adjust the payment which is much advantaged to the teachers' part. The school offers much more from the school budget based on the enrollment in that particular year to augment teachers' compensation.

The Relationship among Socio-Demographic Profile, Priority, Family Condition, and the Indicators Influencing Turnout of Teachers

The results of the chi-square test of the data incorporating those of the variables of the socio-demographic profile and the indicators influencing the turnout of teachers are gleaned in Table 5 and have a significant effect on the teachers' turnout. The socio-demographic profile, and teachers' priority in life and their family conditions affect the satisfaction level of the teachers in terms of their working condition, career path development, and compensation.

A. Relationship among Socio-Demographic Profile, Priority and Family Condition, and the Satisfaction Level of Teachers in Terms of Working Conditions, Career Path Development, and Compensation

Table 5a. Distribution of the Significant Relationship among Socio-Demographic Profile

Relationship among Socio-Demographic Profile			
a. Socio-Demographic Profile	-value	p-value	Interpretation
	($\alpha=0.05$)		
Age	9.297	0.010	Significant
Sex	9.757	0.002	Significant
Civil Status	14.297	0.000	Significant
Length of Service	7.189	0.027	Significant
Degree Earned	52.189	0.000	Significant
b. Teachers' Priority and Family Condition	-value	p-value	Interpretation
	($\alpha=0.05$)		

Priority in Life	57.135	0.000	Significant
Breadwinner	1.324	0.250	Significant

In terms of the socio-demographic profile of the respondents, with the degree of freedom, the probability value of which is higher than the significance level of 0.05. On this basis, there is a significant relationship between the socio-demographic profile of the respondent's satisfaction level in terms of the indicators influencing the turnout of teachers. These findings connote that the socio-demographic profile varies in terms of age level, sex, status in life, the length of service the teachers rendered, and the degree/programs earned because each teacher differs in so many ways. The satisfaction level of the individual matters in their unique personality and the needs and wants to define the teachers. The socio-demographics had a significant influence on the teachers' turnout. The results suggest that socio-demographic factors are important variables to identify the satisfaction and dissatisfaction level of the indicators of their turnout. These variables affect the decision of the respondents to continue or to discontinue their service to the school. It has been shown that the socio-demographic profile is a very important factor in evaluating the respondents' decision to rate their responses to the different indicators in the questionnaire and their answers to the focus group discussion questions.

The results of the chi-square test of the data incorporating the variables of teachers' priority and family condition, and the satisfaction level in terms of the indicators influencing turnout of teachers as gleaned from the table, has a significant relationship among teachers' priority and family condition, and the indicators influencing turnout of teachers. However, in terms of being the breadwinner which is higher than the significance level of 0.05, findings conveyed that being the breadwinner matters, each teacher has its own different needs and wants. Being the breadwinner is significant for the majority of the respondents who supported their families through the financial crisis and the main reason for their turnout to look for greener pastures in public schools to provide for their families. The respondents wanted to fulfill their **obligations or multiple demands on time, energy, or available resources**.

The distribution of the significant relationship among the socio-demographic profile of the respondents matters most in their turnout. The age of the respondents has an impact on their decision to stay and to continue their service to the school. Sex has a great effect on the learning process of the students due to less male authority in the classroom. Their civil status has influenced their career and their professional growth. The length of service is not an assurance that the teachers will stay due to their experience and the years of service they rendered to the school. Their degree qualifies them to teach even with or without master units or doctoral units.

The respondent's priority in life and family condition is focused more on their responsibilities and concern for their families which are very significant that influence their turnout.

Significant Difference in Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction Levels among Indicators of Teachers' Turnout

A. Working Condition

The significant difference among the indicators influencing teacher turnout in terms of working conditions with the degree of freedom, the probability value of χ^2 is lower than the significance level of 0.05.

Table 5b. Significant Differences between the Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction Levels of the Indicators on Working Condition

Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction Levels of the Indicators on Working Condition			
Indicators	-value ($\alpha=0.05$)	p-value	Interpretation
Admin Support	11.242	0.010	Significant
Merits & Awards	3.882	0.274	Not Significant
Relationship with Colleagues	27.324	0.000	Significant
Student Attitude	13.625	0.009	Significant
Teaching Load	6.257	0.100	Not Significant

Table 5b indicated that administrative support, relationship with colleagues, and student attitude have significant differences in the satisfaction level of the indicators on working conditions among the respondents. The result connotes that the working conditions have a strong impact on former tenured teachers as they fully and moderately met their expectations. However, the indicators on merits and awards and the teaching load were not significant to the respondents. They feel that the service they rendered to the school was not given equal merits and awards and their teaching load did not compensate for the compensation they received.

B. Career Path Development

The significant difference among the indicators influencing teacher turnout in terms of career path development with the degree of freedom, the probability value of χ^2 is lower than the significance level of 0.05.

Table 5c. Significant Differences among the Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction Levels of the Indicators on Career Path Development

Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction Levels of the Indicators on Career Path Development			
Indicators	-value ($\alpha=0.05$)	p-value	Interpretation
Educational & Technical Advancement	5.250	0.154	Not Significant
Personal & Spiritual Growth Development	47.105	0.000	Significant
Professional Advancement and Development	16.818	0.001	Significant

Promotional & Career Growth Goals	5.250	0.154	Not Significant
Training & Seminar Enhancement	7.857	0.049	Significant

Table 5c indicated that personal and spiritual growth advancement, professional advancement and development, and training and seminars enhancement have significant differences in the satisfaction level of the indicators on the career path development among the respondents. The result reveals that these indicators are significant to the respondents for they were concerned about their professional and personal growth as teachers. However, the indicators on the educational and technical advancement and promotion and career growth goals were not significant to the respondents as they did not meet their expectations and needed to be observed to minimize teachers' turnout. They wanted to enhance their educational and technical skills as well as the development and security of their career.

C. Compensation

The significant difference among the indicators influencing teacher turnout in terms of compensation with the degree of freedom, the probability value of χ^2 is lower than the significance level of 0.05 to all the indicators.

Table 5d. Significant Differences between the Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction Levels of the Indicators on Compensation

Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction Levels of the Indicators on Compensation			
Indicators	-value ($\alpha=0.05$)	p-value	Interpretation
Salary Adequately Met the Needs of the Teachers	8.000	0.180	Significant
Salary was Comparable to the Public School	17.483	0.001	Significant
Salary was Equitable to the Job	19.333	0.000	Significant
Salary was on Time	35.243	0.000	Significant

Table 5d presents that the indicators on compensation have significant differences in the dissatisfaction level of the indicators on the compensation among the respondents. The results implied that respondents were not compensated well based on the service they rendered to the school. The compensation they received was not comparable to the public school as to the fact public school teachers are generally better paid and have superior pension programs compared to private schools. The compensation varies, which is why due to higher salaries and better benefits packages, teachers gravitate toward public schools to provide the needs and to support the needs of their families which influence teachers' turnout since it did not fully meet their expectations.

CONCLUSION

The length of service the teacher spends in school does not guarantee that teachers will stay in an institution. Families were their priority in life and supporting the needs of their family is a significant factor. Needs when satisfactorily met have a great influence on teachers' continued service to the school. Career pathing and promotion can also be a holding factor despite a lower salary. Moreover, the implementation of the K to12 and the opening of the Senior High School in the new Baybay City Division offered teaching opportunities and vacant items to teachers' applicants. These factors contributed to teachers' turnout.

Additional incentives to suffice the teachers' needs and the right policies are measures to be taken to minimize teachers' turnout.

Based on the findings and the conclusions of the study, the following measures are recommended:

1. Balance the number of male and female teachers to avoid gender disparity and promote the strong influence of teachers to students on sex roles.
2. Improve teachers' incentives and benefits to uplift their morale.
3. Develop a better promotion policy for the teachers based on merit and teaching experiences to uplift teachers' career growth goals.
4. Adopt the proposed faculty development program to minimize teachers' turnout.

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